

Comparative Analysis of Academic Performance between Day Scholars and Hostelites Undergraduate Nursing Students at Public Teaching Institutes of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION: Academic performance is considered as the index of knowledge gained and success achieved in one’s studies, so it is important to know how it is affected by different factors. Student learning is affected by their study habits, motivation to learn, institution type, socioeconomic status, parenting style, family support, sleep and many others. One of the most influencing factors is the environment in which student lives and learns. Students

either live at their homes with parents and only come to college for attending lectures and then return back to their homes, or either they leave their homes and families, and resides in hostels for the purpose of their studies. Both the day scholars and hostelites are the students struggling to perform academically well but in a totally different environment; one has good food, family support, sufficient sleep and no homesickness while the other faces a whole new environment, new roommates, peers, homesickness, altered sleep and eating, stress, and dedicated time for studies. As there are many influencing factors in both home and hostel that affect student’s academic performance so this study aimed to assess and compare academic performances of students as both hostelites and day scholars. **OBJECTIVE:** The objective of this study was to assess and

compare the academic performance among day scholars & hostelites undergraduate nursing students at public teaching institutes in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY: A comparative study was conducted in three public teaching institutes of Peshawar. The duration of study was six months from September, 2025 to December, 2025. Structured Self-Report Rating Scale (Academic Performance) was used to collect data. The data were then analyzed using SPSS version 27. **RESULTS:** A sample of 235 students was studied out of which 149 were hostelites and 86 were day scholars. The results of the study showed that there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the academic performance of hostelites (mean: 28.5705, SD: 2.49663) and day scholars (mean: 28.4186, SD: 2.65448). **CONCLUSION:** There was no significant difference in the academic performance of both hostelites and day scholars nursing students of public teaching institutes of Peshawar, Pakistan. Academic performance of nursing students is not affected by their residency type.

INTRODUCTION

The hostel system was started by Roman Catholics and Anglicans in 20th century. The purpose of hostel system was that whenever the student's needed they could approach to their teachers for any help in academic performances, in their character building, their confidence building, and to cope with new environment and become socially active. They observe good outcomes from students that their confidence level increases and they become more independent in their decision-making skills (1)

Similarly, in Fiji, situated near the south Pacific Ocean, places great emphasis on educating their youth and decided to relocate students to urban areas where they live in dorms. However, due to limitations in providing quality education, especially in rural areas, Initially, students feel like prisoners, but overtime, they adjusted to the new environment. The hostel offers various facilities, including academic assistance programs, libraries, and effective administration, which help students achieve their goals (2). There are many factors that affect the academic performance such as food, environment, socioeconomic status, family support, stress, sleep, distance from institution, and homesickness. These factors greatly influence the hostelites as well as day scholars' academics (3)

The hostelites pass through grief of homesickness and fear of adjustment in new environment, changes in eating and sleeping habits, and adjustment with new people i.e. roommates which affects their physical and mental health and academics also. Besides negative impact, there are some factors that positively affect them for example the new environment as well as peer gave the students a healthy competitive environment and a sense of adaptability in every situation (4)

Similarly, Day scholars, living at home, they are considered as having family support, good food to eat, no stress of homesickness, a balanced diet, and regular sleep, which can positively impacts their overall wellbeing and academic performance while there are some factors that negatively effects them for example the students that are living at a long distance from the institution faces problems of transport, sometimes due to weather changes they can't manage to reach college on time, as they do not suffer from homesickness but sometimes social gatherings and family functions disturb them and their routines (5)

According to some researches the hostellite are affected by emotional disturbances which greatly affect their personalities development (6). Apart from it, the socioeconomic status is another major factor which might affect students' performance, the students from higher socioeconomic status have better access to educational resources which enhance their learning experience but the students from the lower socioeconomic status faces financial constraints which can lead to stress, decreased motivation, and lower access to resources which ultimately affect their academic performance. (7)

Although there are some studies available on the comparison of academic performance between hostelites and day scholars' students but their results are inconsistent. Moreover, no study is available at the local level. The aim to conduct this research was that there were limited studies available on the comparison of academic performance of nursing hostelites and day scholar's students as most of these comparative studies were conducted on students other than nursing. Along with limited studies, the available literature had inconsistency in their results as a study conducted in 2022 showed that hostelites performed academically better than day scholars (5)

On the other hand, some researchers believe that day scholars also perform well as the family support and good food also have good effect on the academic performance (1). This study may also provide valuable insights into the complex relationship between environmental factors, student lifestyles, economic status and academic success which can support in policy decision making and can enable tailored interventions and strategies to enhance academic performance. (8)

1.1 Objectives

- To assess the academic performance among day scholars & hostelites undergraduate nursing students at public teaching institutes in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan
- To compare the academic performance of day scholars and hostelites undergraduate nursing students at public teaching institutes in Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

1.2 Research Question

is there a significant difference in academic performance of hostellite and day scholars undergraduate nursing students studying in public teaching hospitals Peshawar, KPK, Pakistan?

1.3 Operational Definitions

1.3.1 Hostelite: Hostelite refers to a person who live in a hostel, typically a student living away from home for academic purpose.

1.3.2 Day Scholars: Day Scholar refers to a person who attends educational institution during the day but returns home after classes on daily basis, they live at home with their family rather than in hostel.

1.3.3 Academic Performance: Academic performance refers to how well a student understands information, applies skills to tasks, and stay motivated to keep learning with consistent efforts which will be measured through Self-Report Rating Scale.

2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the relevant review on academic performance of hostellites and day scholars nursing students. A descriptive review method was used to evaluate the existent reflection of data available on academic performance of hostellites and day

scholars nursing students and also the factors that affect them. This chapter begins with a general overview regarding academic performance of hostellite and day scholar nursing students across the globe.

2.2 Review Method

Literature review is the summarizing of the available studies related to the research topic. Our study includes past research, published works, and relevant content from different perspectives on the subject. The literature review helps to understand the depth of the issue, identify existing knowledge, and highlight the gaps that is to be filled with certain interventions.

2.3 Objectives of Literature Review

The main objectives of the literature review were:

1. To search global literature on academic performance of hostellite and day scholars undergraduate nursing students and its magnitude in the public teaching institute of Peshawar, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan
2. To search literature on the factors affecting academic performance of hostellite and day scholars undergraduate nursing students

2.4 Search Strategy

The key words used in search were hostellites, day scholars, academic performance, and factors affecting academic performance. Latest search engine including Google Scholar, PubMed, and CINHALL were used. The literature was decided on the basis of inclusion and exclusion criteria. Majority of the literatures were taken from 2019 to 2025 but few older articles were also taken due to their relevancy.

2.5 Introduction

Hostellites are the students that are living in hostels while day scholars are the students that are living at their homes with their families (1). Hostel life affects students' health and academic achievement. Positively, students prefer staying in hostels due to improved educational facilities, systematic learning process, and exposure to personal development opportunities. Peer support groups in hostels are likely to promote collaborative learning, improve self-development, and enhance academic motivation. Negatively, hostel life is full of challenges.

A study conducted by Iqbal et al. found that peer pressure, social disruptions, and economic pressures could adversely affect the mental well-being and academic achievements of the students. These stressors can lead to emotional distress, poor concentration, and low academic achievement. The study emphasizes the need for effective hostel administration and policy measures grounded in science to establish well-supportive, inclusive, and psychologically safe environments. Additionally, authors recommend inter-disciplinary collaboration between hostel institutions, policymakers, and stakeholders in an effort to alleviate hostel-induced stressors as well as improve the academic achievement and overall well-being of students (2).

A study investigated the question of whether a general cognitive ability (g) test would be a reliable predictor of success in school and work environments. The study used the Miller Analogies Test (MAT) as an estimate of g and compared its predictive validity for 18 schooling and work-related accomplishments, including standardized tests like the GRE (Graduate Record Examinations). The results reaffirmed that general cognitive ability always predicts broad samples of measures of attainment, ranging from academic attainment through occupational performance, career success, and creative ability. The authors concluded the implication that g is a stable and transferable predictor of attainment in a broad range of life areas, noting that the type of intelligence brought to school is really the same type that is brought to business life. These findings support the general superiority of cognitive ability as a predictor of personal success across situational context and area (9).

Similarly, another study carried out comparative research with the objective of contrasting the personality dynamics of boarder students and day scholars studying in Lahore public universities using the NEO (Noncombatant Evacuation Operations) Personality Inventory as the measuring tool. The results indicated that there were considerable differences between the two student populations: boarder students were less expressive, while more ambitious, and outgoing than day scholars. Other than that, humanities and male students showed higher personality development compared to others. In the study, hostel life in certain instances might confine socialization and personal development because of limited autonomy and social exposure. The authors suggested having official counseling and mentorship schemes in hostels to ensure

boarder students' social and emotional growth and, in the long run, develop a balanced and adaptive personality profile (10).

Additionally, a cross-sectional study used to investigate factors that affect academic performance among medical students. Results showed that the best-performing students spent more time engaging in hobbies and sports and much less time on social media. Furthermore, factors including good study habits, sufficient sleep duration, where they lived, and possessing parents who were doctors were in strong correlation with better academic performance. The research highlighted the importance of lifestyle and environmental influences as key determinants of students' academic achievement, implying that well-balanced daily regimens, favorable living conditions, and positive behavioral habits play a significant role in improved performance in medical education (11).

Furthermore, a study to compare study skills between day scholars and hostel students in nursing education through a standardized questionnaire of 418 participants. The findings showed hostel students excelled in every aspect of study skills except test preparation and note-taking, where day scholars excelled. The research found hostel dwellers with better educational advancements and better learning habits in general. The authors added that hospitality in hostel environments is to be attributed for better learning abilities and academic achievements of students (12).

A study conducted a comparative investigation on day scholar and hostel-dwelling medical undergraduate students' academic performance at Saveetha Medical College, Chennai. According to both theory and practical examination results, in the study it was observed that day scholars outperformed hostel students on average, with fewer students scoring below 50%. Based on the results, it was inferred that residential status was a major determinant of academic performance, and because of this, day scholars performed better since structured routines and more caring home environments were incorporated. These diverse results indicate that although hostels offer peer learning and autonomy, the lack of family stability and structure at times can hinder maximum academic performance (13).

Another cross-sectional comparative study in Lahore was conducted to determine the nutritional well-being and academic performance of day scholars and hostelers of allied

health sciences. On the basis of survey results from 171 respondents, the study revealed day scholars were physically healthier compared to hostelers, while hostelers were slightly more performing academically. The findings indicated that hostel life affects health as well as academic performance with academically enhancing hostel students more affected by health issues compared to day scholars (5).

Similarly, a study in Uttar Pradesh analyzed that hostel and day scholar students' difference level of adjustment 14 to 15 years Meerut District, Uttar Pradesh. As per Bell's Adjustment Inventory on a sample of 600 students, the study contrasted home, health, social, and emotional adjustment by using mean, standard deviation, and t-tests. The results indicated very huge differences between the two groups on all three scales, indicating that residence is making a worthwhile contribution to adolescents' total adjustment and well-being (14). Another study compared the academic performance of boarders and day scholars in a private medical college in Faisalabad using the retrospective comparative design. Aggregate mean score categories were employed in examining data among 214 students from first and second years. Day scholars indicated a higher academic score than boarders, indicating that home environment has a positive effect on academic performance. The research concluded that student's home-staying were more successful in their studies than hostel residents (1)

The study examined the relationship between sleep quality and academic performance among Peshawar Medical College's Day scholars and residents of the hostel of medical undergraduate students. Based on self-rated academic performance and the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI), the study illustrated that 69.3% of the students reported poor sleep quality, with hostel residents reporting significantly worse sleep than day scholars. Further, students who witnessed improved quality of sleep also achieved higher grades in class, and gender differences were statistically insignificant. The research presented that hostel students suffering from poor quality of sleep is one of the main reasons for poor academic outcomes (15).

Also, a study has carried out a comparative analysis of 50 students studying nursing in New Delhi to compare differences in health status as well as academic performance among day scholars and hostel dwellers. The findings indicated that hostel students enjoyed improved health, due to parental supervision and exposure to healthy

diets, and hostel students enjoyed improved academic achievement, possibly through group study and decreased commuting time. The research highlighted that health education, counseling, and stress management programs should be utilized in schools of nursing to facilitate students attaining a balanced life of studies and happiness (16).

Furthermore, research conducted to explore the difference in behavior and studies between boarders and day scholars at secondary level based on data gathered from 329 students who were randomly chosen. Results indicated that boarding system students were shown to achieve higher academic engagement and use of institutional facilities, while day scholars experienced difficulties with school-to-school distances to attend and study conditions in homes. Despite the variations, the researchers found that both systems are supported by their own strengths and weaknesses, which show that students' academic and behavioral performance is shaped by institutional and environmental factors combined (17).

Moreover, a study investigated determinants and prevalence of depression, anxiety, and stress among Banasthali Vidyapith female hosteller and day scholar students. The observational design was used in the study and hostel social and environmental determinants were identified as major determinants for poor mental health. The results showed that hosteller students were stressed and depressed compared to day scholars and exerted a negative impact on their social and personal health. The study was focused on addressing the risk factors of mental health among hostellers (18).

A cross-sectional comparative study aims to determine day scholars' and hostel students' nutritional status and academic performance while pursuing allied health sciences courses in Lahore. 171 students (77 males, 94 females) took part. Findings indicated hostelites' physical health (36.5%) was inferior to that of day scholars (53.9%), while hostelites' performance (65.5%) was slightly better than that of day scholars (56.4%). It was also concluded from the study that day scholars were healthier because they received home care while hostel life provided more academic success because there were organized study areas (5).

In contrast, hosteller and day scholar health status among 200 Ziauddin University Faculty of Nursing and Midwifery undergraduate nursing students. Data was analyzed

using SPSS (v.22) showing mean health score for hostellers (32.45 ± 4.48) greater than day scholars (30.8 ± 4.28 ; $p = 0.008$), reflecting overall improved hosteller health (19).

Although a study compared gender variations in peer pressure, academic stress, and goal re-engagement between 300 Lahore university students. Outcome showed that day scholars experienced more direct peer pressure and academic stress than hostelites and shifted from unrealistic to realistic goals and re-engage realistic goals. The research aimed to develop healthful learning environments that help students manage academic stress and promote healthful re-engagement of goals (4).

Consequently, a study demonstrated that family and academic stress affect depression level and academic performance of students with the theory of cognitive appraisal of stress of Lazarus. A five-point Likert scale questionnaire was used to collect the responses from a non-probability convenience sample of postgraduate and undergraduate students and was analyzed with structural equation modeling (SEM). Conclusion confirmed that stress both at school and at home contributes significantly to the causation of depression, which also negatively affects academic performance in students. The importance of stressor management in improving mental health and academic performance is highlighted in the study (20).

Additionally, a critical appraisal of the quantitative study that how motivation and self-esteem influence academic engagement and consequently academic achievement in 243 students at university. The results showed that self-esteem influenced emotional and behavioral disengagement but motivation significantly impacted academic engagement, with metacognitive engagement being a strong predictor of academic achievement. The research calls for the need to create metacognitive strategies that will allow students to plan, monitor, and control their learning in a bid to achieve increased academic achievement (8).

Similarly, a cross-sectional study correlates between chrono-nutrition habits, demographic profile, and grades in 288 students of a university with an age group of 18–30 years. The research did not find any statistical association between sleep or eating windows of meals, including skipping breakfast, and grades. It was hypothesized that differences in chrono-nutrition profiles were not indicative of academic achievement and that prospective studies were required to further analyze these correlations (21).

3: MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Study Design: Analytical Cross-sectional study design was used.

3.2 Study Settings: The study was conducted in the three public teaching institutes of Peshawar i.e., Government College of Nursing, Hayatabad Medical Complex Peshawar, Government College of Nursing, Khyber Teaching Hospital Peshawar, and Government College of Nursing, Lady Reading Hospital Peshawar.

3.3 Study duration: The duration for this study prevails over a period of six months started from September, 2025 to December, 2025.

3.4 Study population and sample size: Our population was student nurses including both residing in hostel as well as day scholars and the total nursing students were 800 out of which the sample size was calculated 235 with CI 95%, and margin of error 5%. The rate of refusal was assumed as 10%.

3.5 Sampling Technique: Probability sampling technique that is simple random sample was used to sample the population.

3.6 Sample Selection

3.6.1 Inclusion Criteria

➤ Nursing students enrolled in 2nd, 3rd, and final year of Undergraduate Nursing Program in these three public institutes of Peshawar that were willing to participate were included in this study.

3.6.2 Exclusion Criteria

➤ Students who were absent at the time of data collection were excluded.

3.7 Ethical Consideration

Permission letters were signed from the principal of each college. Informed consent was taken both verbally and in written from all the participants.

3.8 Data Collection Procedure

A proportionate sample of 66 students from LRH, 115 students from KTH, and 54 students from HMC who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were selected for the study. After explaining the purpose and objectives of the study, the questionnaire i.e. Structured Self-Report Rating Scale (Academic Progress) were administered among both hostelites and day scholars and they filled that questionnaire.

3.9 Data Analysis Procedure

After data collection, SPSS version 27 was used for data analysis. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for continuous variables while for categorical variables frequencies and percentages were calculated. Data were presented through graphs and charts. For inferential statistics, Independent Sample T-Test and ANOVA were applied.

4: RESULTS

TABLE 4.1: *SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC DATA*

	Frequency	Percentage
College		
LRH	77	32.8
KTH	109	46.4
HMC	49	20.9
Total	235	100
Gender		
Male	17	7.2
Female	218	92.8
Total	235	100
Residency type		
Hostelites	149	63.4
Day Scholars	86	36.6
Total	235	100

The table 4.1 shows the frequencies and percentages on the basis of gender, residency types and the college students.

FIGURE 4.1: COLLEGE STUDENTS

Figure 4.1 shows the college of the participants, according to which 32.8% (77) were admitted in Government College of Nursing, Lady Reading Hospital, 46.4% (109) in Government College of Nursing, Khyber Teaching Hospital and 20.9% (49) were in Government College of Nursing, Hayatabad.

FIGURE 4.2: GENDER

Figure 4.2 shows that 7.2% (17) were male while 92.8% (218) were female participants.

FIGURE 4.3: RESIDENCY TYPES

Figure 4.3 shows the residency of the students that includes hostelites and day scholars. According to this, 63.4% (149) were residing in hostels while 36.6% (86) were day scholars.

TABLE 4.2: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS (PERCENTAGES AND FREQUENCIES) OF LIKERT'S SCALE POINTS REGARDING ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG NURSING STUDENTS:

S.No.	Statements	Often		Sometimes		Never	
		Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age	Frequency	%age
1.	I avoid going to class.	6	2.55	45	19.15	184	78.30
2.	I get attendance more than 70%.	195	82.98	26	11.06	14	5.96
3.	I have been scoring above 65% in all subjects.	179	76.17	52	22.13	4	1.70
4.	I feel sleepy during classes.	21	8.94	150	63.83	64	27.23
5.	I participate in various cultural activities.	23	9.79	113	48.09	99	42.13

6.	I face problems in collecting study material during exams.	35	14.89	112	47.66	88	37.45
7.	I am able to concentrate during classes.	182	77.45	40	17.02	13	5.53
8.	I am not getting time for self-study.	34	14.47	86	36.60	115	48.94
9.	I am able to interact with teachers.	138	58.72	78	33.19	19	8.09
10.	I spend more time in social network, watching TV rather than studying.	48	20.43	133	56.60	54	22.98
11.	I am late to class.	27	11.49	75	31.91	133	56.60
12.	I miss important information discussed in the class.	20	8.51	86	36.60	129	54.89
13.	I avail library facility of my college.	52	22.13	118	50.21	65	27.66
14.	I submit my assignment on time.	198	84.26	32	13.62	5	2.13
15.	I am always punctual for clinical postings.	183	77.87	46	19.57	6	2.55

The table 4.2 shows the frequencies and percentages of responses of the participants to different questions of the questionnaire.

FIGURE 4.4: FREQUENCIES OF CGPA

TABLE 4.3: FREQUENCIES OF CGPA

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
CGPA	235	1.70	2.30	4.00	3.4450	.30276	.092

Valid N (list wise)

The table 4.3 shows the descriptive statistics of CGPA. For 235 students CGPA has a range of 1.70 with a minimum value of 2.30 and a maximum value of 4.00. The mean of CGPA is 3.4450 with a standard deviation of 0.30276 and a variance of 0.092.

TABLE 4.4: GROUP STATISTICS

Group Statistics		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Total score	MALE	17	28.3529	2.87100	.69632
	FEMALE	218	28.5275	2.53122	.17144
Total score	HOSTELITE	149	28.5705	2.49663	.20453
	DAY SCHOLARS	86	28.4186	2.65448	.28624
CGPA	HOSTELITE	149	3.4494	.30792	.02523
	DAY SCHOLAR	86	3.4373	.29522	.03183

The mean score, standard deviation, and standard error mean of the total score of males, female and hostellite & day scholars are mentioned in the table 4.4.

TABLE 4.5: *INDEPENDENT SAMPLE T-TEST*

Independent Samples Test			T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	95% confidence interval	of the difference
						Lower	Upper
Total score (male/female)	Equal variance assumed		-.271	233	.786	-1.44268	1.09351
Total score (hostelite/day scholar)	Equal variance assumed		-.439	233	.661	-.52993	.83366
CGPA (hostelite/day scholar)	Equal variance assumed		.294	233	.769	-.06887	.09301

Independent sample T test was applied to see whether there is a difference between male and female mean score regarding academic performance and it was found to be insignificant as shown in the table 4.5.

TABLE 4.6: *ANOVA*

ANOVA					
total score	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	6.788	2	3.394	.519	.596
Within Groups	1515.909	232	6.534		
Total	1522.698	234			

TABLE 4.7: ANOVA EFFECT SIZES

ANOVA Effect Sizes^{a,b}

		Point Estimate	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower	Upper
total score	Eta-squared	.004	.000	.029
	Epsilon-squared	-.004	-.009	.021
	Omega-squared Fixed-effect	-.004	-.009	.021
	Omega-squared Random-effect	-.002	-.004	.011

a. Eta-squared and Epsilon-squared are estimated based on the fixed-effect model.

b. Negative but less biased estimates are retained, not rounded to zero.

TABLE 4.8: POST HOC TESTS

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: total score

Tukey HSD

(I) college	(J) college	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
LRH	KTH	-.09127	.38053	.969	-.9889	.8064
	HMC	-.46011	.46713	.587	-1.5620	.6418
KTH	LRH	.09127	.38053	.969	-.8064	.9889
	HMC	-.36884	.43965	.679	-1.4059	.6682
HMC	LRH	.46011	.46713	.587	-.6418	1.5620
	KTH	.36884	.43965	.679	-.6682	1.4059

TABLE 4.9: HOMOGENOUS SUBSETS

Total Score

Tukey HSD^{a,b}

College	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05
		1
LRH	77	28.3766
KTH	109	28.4679

HMC	49	28.8367
Sig.		.535

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

- Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 70.473.
- The group sizes are unequal. The harmonic mean of the group sizes is used. Type I error levels are not guaranteed.

5: DISCUSSION

Introduction

This chapter contains a detailed discussion of the study results in relation to the research question and how these results are related to the existing literature regarding the phenomenon of the study. A comparative analytical study was conducted to compare the academic performance of hostelites and day scholars. A sample size of 235 nursing students was selected through simple random sampling and data was collected using Structured Self-Report Rating Scale (academic performance).

Academic Performance

Academic performance is how well a student understands information, applies skills to tasks, and stays motivated to keep learning with consistent efforts (22). Students' academic performance is important to assess student standing in the university and the improvements needed to enhance this standing (23). Different indicators are used to gauge students' academic performance but majority considers grades as indicator of student's success as it reflects accomplishment of specific goals and degree of knowledge acquired in a particular field (24). In this study students' CGPA along with some other indicators such as class attendance, participation in cultural activities, punctuality to clinical rotation, concentration in class lectures and timely submission of assignment are taken into consideration to assess the academic performance of the nursing students.

For the comparison of academic performance, data was collected from a sample of 235 nursing students which included 86-day scholars and 149 hostelite nursing students using Self-Report Rating Scale (academic performance). It measured the academic performance among the selected demographic variables.

The results of this study showed that there is no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the academic performance of hostelites and day scholars hence it failed to reject the null hypothesis. According to this study both hostelites and day scholars performed independent of their residency of living. Most of the literature available on the comparison of academic performance of hostelites and day scholars is in contrast to this study as a study conducted showed there is a significant difference in the academic performance of hostelites and day scholars (14). According to some studies hostelites perform academically better (12) while according to others day scholars are the high performer and have better study habits as they are blessed with proper facilities at home helping them to concentrate more on their studies (25). Similarly, a retrospective comparative study conducted in Faisalabad showed that overall aggregate results of day scholars is more than hostelites ($p < 0.0001$) (1). Over-all adjustment including home, health, social, emotional and educational level adjustment of day scholars is better than hostelites (26). Studies suggest that sleep pattern affects academic achievements, good sleepers perform academically better than poor sleepers with p -value: 0.002). Day scholars perform academically better as they have good sleep pattern than hostelites (15). In contrast a study of Lahore claimed that day scholars experience more academic stress and refrain from unattainable goals as compared to hostelites (4).

Though there are many studies favoring day scholars some studies support hostelites as a study conducted in New Delhi showed that 84% hostellers are good in academics while in case of day scholars only 80% are good, the reasons for hostelites performing better can be less travel time, group studies and help from hostel mates (16). This assumption is supported by another study conducted in Allied Health Sciences Students of Lahore, where academic performance of hostelites was 65.5% better and academic performance of day scholars was 56.4% (5). Another study of 2023 also showed higher academic performance and better study habits in hostelites ($t: -5.16$, $p < 0.05$) (27). Similarly, a study discussed the major problems faced by day scholars which include long distance from home, food and space availability, lack of parents' attention towards education of their child, and environment for study. To compensate these problems boarding system is better to improve academics (17). However, hostels have many advantages but their disadvantages outnumber so for better overall benefits

of academics, physical and psychological health, one should go for other option rather than hostel (2). A study in a medical university also showed that hostelites were taking more supplementary exams (0.009) and were having average score ($p < 0.001$) less than day scholars (28). Another study of Pakistan also showed lower overall mean aggregate of hostel students than day scholars with a p value < 0.001 (1). Apart from this, GPA is negatively affected by psychological factors such as anxiety, stress and substance abuse (29) and a study conducted in Banasthali University showed that hostelites are more vulnerable to mental stress and dilemmas (18). Day scholars, on the other hand, have more positive personality dynamics such as conscientiousness, neuroticism, extraversion, agreeableness and openness (10).

On the contrary to these studies, the study conducted in Rehman Medical College, Peshawar found insignificant difference in the mean marks of both professional and pre-professional examinations of hostelites and day scholars (30). The results of their study are similar with the current study. Similarly, another study was conducted in the same college and it compared academic performance of hostelites and day scholars on the basis of pharmacology examinations. The results found no significant difference which resonates with the results of this study (31). Another study conducted in India concluded that both hostelites and day scholars are good at their level and found no significant difference in their social adjustment and academic progress (32).

On the basis of all the literature discussed, it can be inferred that residential status alone does not affect the academic performance, as there many other confounding factors which influences the overall academic performance of both hostelites and day scholar students. Academic performance is influenced by parenting styles as authoritative parenting enhances academic performances (33) (34). Similarly, academic performance also depends on the individual habits and motivations of the students as performance is enhanced 34% due to extrinsic motivation and 23% due to intrinsic motivation (35). Other factors that affect academic performance includes gender, high school grade, student's parental education, financial background, medium of teaching, student's family status, living location, students' previous semester marks, seminar performance class, test grade, assignment performance, attendance in class and lab work, general proficiency, Interest in particular course, Study behavior, Engage Time

and Family Support for study, previous schools marks, admission type, parent's occupation, parent's qualification. (23). High performer spends less time on social – networking sites and engage more in their hobbies and physical activities, and have different sleep and study habits than average-performer (11). Therefore, the performance of students in both hostel and homes depends not only on their area of living but also on how much they are influenced by all the other factors.

6: CONCLUSION

Both Hostelites and Day Scholars live in a different environment and face different factors which may affect their academic performance. In past, boarding system was introduced so that hostelites have access to teachers in times of need. The purpose was to improve students' academic performance, so different studies were conducted across the global to check whether it actually improves the academics or not. Different studies suggested contrasting results that is some showed that the hostelites are good performers while other favored day scholars and there were some studies suggesting that academic performance is independent of residency of living. The purpose to conduct this study was to compare the academic performance of hostelites and day scholar nursing students at public institutes of Peshawar. Data were collected from a representative sample using Self-Report Rating Scale (Academic Performance) and it was then statistically analyzed. The results of this study revealed that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of hostelites and day scholars nursing students. Both performed independently and their studies and exams were not affected by their residency type. There was no significant difference in their mean CGPA and their other academic activities, such as participation in cultural activities, timely submission of assignments, maintaining class attendance, self-study, concentrating during lectures and interacting with the teachers.

STRENGTHS OF THE STUDY

- Random probability sampling technique was used which represents the entire population and can be easily generalized to the study population.
- This is the first study conducted on the nursing students in the local context.

- The sample size of the study was 235 which was calculated through internationally recognized software Raosoft software which is a good representative of study population and is applicable for generalizability.
- In this study the CGPA was not considered the only indicator of academic performance but other aspects were also included i.e. punctuality, co-curricular activities, attendance, submission of assignment, concentration in class and many others which encompasses major areas of academic performance.

WEAKNESS OF THE STUDY

- The study assumes that the academic performance can be fully measured on the basis of CGPA, class attendance and co-curricular activities while ignoring the practical skills and clinical competence which limits the broader aspects of students' overall performance.
- The study may be influenced by factors specific to Peshawar such that cultural and socioeconomic difference.
- The study may not account for other factors that could impact the academic performance, such as individual student characteristics, teaching quality, and institutional resources.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- Data was collected only from the public sector students if data were collected from both public and private sector students it might have revealed a significant difference.
- The time duration of the study was limited, we were in rush to complete the study, it would have been better to get the sufficient time to conduct the quality study.

NURSING IMPLICATIONS

- The study's findings may inform the development of targeted support services for hostellites, such as academic counseling, mental health support, and study skills workshops.
- Nurse educators can use the study's findings to identify students who may be at risk of poor academic performance and provide targeted support.

- The study highlights the importance of considering the well-being of nursing students, particularly hostellites, and the need for institutions to provide resources to support their mental and physical health.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of results of the study, the following are the recommendations are suggested:

- Data were only collected from public sector colleges it would be better to collect data from both private and public institutions in the future studies to explore how different types of institutions affect the academic performance.
- The study was conducted only on the basis of CGPA, class attendance, and co-curricular activities, for future researchers it is advised to incorporate other variables like practical skills and clinical competence as well.
- In this research the factors influencing academic performance were not discussed so it is recommended that further researches should focus on analysis of different factors like study habits, parenting styles, and socioeconomic background etc. and their impact on academic performance.
- Quantitative data analysis was used in this study; it is suggested for future researchers to use both mixed-method design to gather deeper understanding of student's academic performance.

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